

EXAKI

The EXA4MIND Kickstarter initiative

EXAKI is the knowledge centre for implementing EXA4MIND technologies in research and industry. It provides training, documentation, and practical guidance to help researchers, SMEs, and IT professionals integrate extreme data analytics into their applications.

Through EXAKI, users can:

Learn how to choose and deploy modules of the EXA4MIND software stack.

Access technical documentation, webinars, and hands-on training sessions.

Join a community of experts pushing the boundaries of data analytics in Europe.

EXAKI makes the results of EXA4MIND accessible across disciplines – from molecular dynamics and smart agriculture to automotive systems and health data mining.

EXA4MIND.EU

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VS^B TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA | IT4INNOVATIONS NATIONAL SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER

 Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities

 ORTA DOĞU TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

 AUSTRALO

EURAXENT

Valeo

 terraviewos

 CTU CZECH TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY IN PRAGUE

alt:nativ

EXA4MIND

Building the platform for Extreme Data

Funded by
the European Union

**DEVELOPING A SOLUTION
FOR EXTREME DATA
THAT ENABLES
ADVANCED DATA ANALYTICS
ON SUPERCOMPUTERS AND
AUTOMATED DATA MANAGEMENT**

Why EXA4MIND?

In an age of exploding data volumes, Europe faces the challenge of ensuring digital sovereignty for business, science, and R&D. While the continent's most powerful supercomputers are primarily used for simulations, their potential for large-scale data analytics often remains untapped.

EXA4MIND bridges this gap by bringing together universities, supercomputing centres, and application providers from science, industry, and SMEs. The project lays the foundation for an Extreme Data platform that connects large-scale storage systems with high-performance computing infrastructures, opening the door to advanced analytics, machine learning, and AI at scale.

Our Mission

To deliver a platform for Extreme Data that enables advanced analytics on supercomputers, automated data management, and seamless integration with EOSC and European Data Spaces.

Our Vision

To create long-term impact in world-leading data and computing technologies by spearheading key enablers for a digital, sustainable, and human-centric paradigm shift, positioning Europe at the forefront of the data revolution.

Scientific

Molecular dynamics – innovative fast processing of large molecular dynamics simulations on cloud and HPC.

- **ADAMS4SIMS**, an innovative Automated Data Mining System for Systematic Improvement of Molecular simulations accuracy and predictability, will combine services and on-/offline data sources.

Data: 0.1–1 PB range

SME Agricultural

Aquaview – Enabling sensor less soil moisture analysis at scale

- Easy and quick ingestion of large amounts of **agriculture focused** data, as well as efficient and space-saving re-distribution of computed/ingested (meta-)data.

Data: 0.01–1 PB range

Industrial

Using HPC for training AI models for automated exploration of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems validation data to increase safety on

- **Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS)** need Extreme Data annotation, search and analytics. Methods, AI models and framework are co-developed in EXA4MIND.

Data: 1–100 PB range

Secure Health Data Mining

ETL + EXA4MIND EDD Integration – Leveraging EXA4MIND & Supercomputing to Deliver Actionable Extreme Data Insights

- Demonstration of viability of **Extreme Data Database (EDD)** for Extreme Data processing use cases with health and societal datasets, based on direct user interaction.

Data: 0.01–0.1 PB range